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Experience of Self-Understanding as a Humanities Block of Professional Development

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Abstract

The problem of formation of self-understanding by future teachers was studied in many humanities topics in modern education and establishes higher academic requirements to professional teachers. Computers and information technologies have changed the nature of professional activity of educators so they should share ideas of humanities as a “human measure” of education. This teacher expert is aware to be an instrument of professional activity and is able to apply principle of humanities. The principle means the unity of noninterference into the inner world of a child and influence on his or her value- meaningful sphere. The research is aimed to give foundation from the point of view of anthropological and humanities approach, interdisciplinary knowledge of cognitive sciences, the experience of self-understanding of the humanities block of professional development of future teachers and reveal the conditions for formation this experience at the university. The research uses methods of analysis, questionnaires, project testing, observation, dialogue, and content-analysis. Three hundred twenty students of the Kalmyk State University named after B.B. Gorodovikov participated in the experiment. The article and its results may be of great interest for post-graduates and graduates of pedagogical faculty making research in the field of humanity principle of education and also can be used in projecting basic educational programs for future teachers and professional development of educators.

Keywords: humanity principle of education, the experience of self-understanding, psychological rationality, anthropological practice, textual-dialogue method, spiral dynamics method.

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Introduction

In a changing world with its global processes most spheres and systems of social life require not a superficial, but a fundamental renovation. Nowadays the teacher's professional and pedagogical activity also requires changes that consider a new comprehension of goals and results of education reflected in a number of documents on education reforms in Russia and in the world with the aim of achieving a new quality of education (Valeeva & Gafurov, 2017). An important issue on the agenda at present is the question of personality of a teacher and the essence of his or her pedagogical work. This is the problem of teacher's ability to be a “conductor” of necessary changes in education.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The aim of the investigation is to develop a model of formation of future teachers' experience of self-discovery. Tasks: 1) to substantiate the experience of self-discovery as a humanitarian constituent of the professional education content of the future teacher; 2) to determine criteria and diagnostic methods of the investigated process; 3) to develop and approbate a model of formation of future teachers' experience of self-discovery in university professional education process.

Literature review

There are many fundamental works on the problem of teacher's professionalism, professional and personal self-development. In particular, the following issues are considered: self-development of teacher's personality and building his or her own strategy for professional growth (Markova, 1993); the formation of his or her ability to transform his or her own life activity into practical objects (Mitina, 2020); value-semantic and target dominants of humanistically-oriented professional-pedagogical activity (Kolesnikova, 1999). The ways to improve teacher's professional abilities are proposed in different approaches: axiological and cultural (Isaev & Shiyanov, 2005), competence (Zimnyaya, 2000; Sayfullina & Valeeva, 2019), personality-oriented (Serikov, 2016). But this problem requires a thorough analysis from the viewpoint of the humanitarian-anthropological approach in the context of psychology of consciousness (Akopov, 2010) and cognitive research (Clarín, 2017). The question of the formation of teacher's professionalism and his or her experience of self-discovery included in the structure of pedagogical education content still remains open.

Methodology

The search for knowledge on the phenomenon of self-discovery experience as a humanitarian constituent of pedagogical education content and the features of the formation of this experience requires an appeal to interdisciplinary fields of cognitive research that gives a new start in methodology.

The anthropological constituent of pedagogical methodology embodies the humanitarian methodology, which "... arose as a result of scientific reflection of new humanistic, personality-oriented tendencies (Bondarevskaya, 2000). Humanitarian methodology is based on humanistic philosophy.

The cognitive learning is based on the principles of consciousness and activity of the individual in an educational situation, on procedures and strategies that recognize the importance of metacognition and mediating processes (Clarín, 2017). It covers the problem of fundamental relationship of human cognition with the properties of the nervous system embodied in the body (Lakoff & Johnson, 1999).

It is worth mentioning that in traditional university training practice of the future teacher the focus should be on understanding of the particular subject without considering such factors as connection and "metacognition" that are associated with cognition of the cogniser himself or herself. Here a rhetorical question arises: what kind of knowledge can one acquire if he or she does not fully realize himself as a subject of obtaining this knowledge and as a bearer of subjective reality?!

In modern philosophy and cognitive sciences we consider the shift towards phenomenology, the study of the subjective features of the experience of individual consciousness (self-awareness) (Anokhin, 2015; Clarín, 2017; Knyazeva, 2011). The cognitive act for each person is always unique as it on the inner level and is not always fully realized. In its structure, as in the structure of personal knowledge (Polani, 1985), the most essential is its implicit plan that is accessible to the phenomenological methods of self-discovery.

During the consideration of the research methods we relied on the experience of self-discovery in the context of metacognitive processes that are quite difficult to study. Metacognitive processes do not have their "final product"; they are not revealed in activities, behavior, communication, but can be indirectly observed through one of the important cognitive processes – attention. We have developed author's methods that allow students to study and form the experience of self-discovery through the work with their own attention.

Among them are discourse analysis techniques. As a set of analytical methods for interpreting texts and statements of various kinds the discourse analysis was originated from linguistics, sociology and psychoanalysis on the basis of the works in this field.

As an example of the author's methods used in our investigation we can denote the projective method of discourse analysis "My goal". This is a series of consistently unfolding questions that allow to attract our attention to internal objects that are not given in awareness: "What do think about ...?"; "How did you understand this (a)?"; "What does this mean to you?"; "What it will bring to you?"; "How do you feel about this?"; "Why is it important to you?"; "Why do you need this?". Thus, a person has the opportunity to realize the levels of his thinking: cognitive, value, emotional, bodily-energetic, pragmatic.

We are dealing with humanitarian methods that assume an internal locus of control and cannot be always rationalized. Therefore, in the work with students the most important result is not only a given reply but a question that allows them to be more reflexive.

Based on the ideas of the anthropology of education, knowledge of humanitarian model of education, concept of personal knowledge and interdisciplinary field of cognitive research, we have determined that the experience of self-discovery as a humanitarian constituent of a future teacher's education content includes the cognition of the content, functions and the structure of one's consciousness.

The consciousness in this case is considered to be an integrative way of existence of human being manifested in his or her ability to master the conditions and forms of his or her life, regard them as a subject of practical transformation (Slobodchikov, 2005). We also consider informational mental processes that are carried out by the brain and associated with the content of information and the properties of its "material object" (Akopov, 2010). This allows us to consider teacher's professional and pedagogical consciousness as the ability to reach the level of self-reflection in accordance with the context of professional activity and management of one's professional and personal development. Its development begins with self-discovery. Person's cognition of oneself presupposes the cognition of three stages of subjective reality: 1) sensations, emotions, thoughts, experiences, images, ideas, relationships ("what is in my inner world"); 2) peculiarities of attention, perception, thinking, imagination, memory, feelings, reaction ("how I function in this world"); 3) personal position, I-image, I-concept, integrity ("who I am").

Considering a person as a "bio-psycho-socio-spiritual system" in the context of "noetic dynamics" as an 8-level scale of values (Beck & Cowan, 2010), we understand that such cognition occurs on the bodily-physiological, emotional-psychological, cognitive-linguistic, activity-creative levels. Essentially, the process of self-discovery is intended for an individual as a conscious modeling of his own world-picture on the basis of understanding his needs, motives, attitudes, ideas, values, meanings, goals that are correlated with the internal environment and external circumstances according to his productive activity and creative realization.

The mechanism that ensures the formation of the experience of self-discovery is the textual-dialogical educational activity in which the person has the ability to realize himself or herself as the "author" and "addressee" of the statement, and the method of spiral-dynamic self-investigation.

The "spiral-dynamic model" of self-investigation takes a special place among others. It allows a person to study his or her own "organizing principle" and monitor self-discovery levels in accordance with value dominants. The material for this kind of research are narrative texts as a form of systematization of subjective information. The narrative allows the person to organize information on the world and himself or herself, to arrange random facts and phenomena in a certain sequence of events, to create such a coherent and complete story that gives the person a deeper understanding of himself or herself (Znakov, 2011; Sarbin, 2004; Landau et al., 2004).

Our research has been carried out on the basis of the Kalmyk State University for four years. Undergraduate and postgraduate students of the programme "Pedagogical Education" take part in this project. In total, about 400 people (students) were involved in the experiment, at present stage there are 125 people. The test group contains 76 students. The experiment is still on and now it is at its final stage. In accordance with the purpose of the investigation, a special program for undergraduate and postgraduate students was developed. This program is aimed to form their experience of self-discovery within the disciplines "Fundamentals of Pedagogical Skills", "Theory and Methods of Teaching Mathematics in Primary School", "Theory and Methods of Teaching Technology at School", "Management of educational systems", etc. While studying these disciplines and project activities at bachelor's and master's programs (projects "People's University", "University of Man of the 21st century", "School of professional development", "Pedagogical debut") students have the opportunity to display themselves in the situations of self-observation, self-exploration, self-management and assess their skills in the given situations. This experience was determined by a system of reflective questions (discourse analysis) in the context of dialogue. In Table 1 a model of formation of future- teachers' self-discovery experience is represented:

Stages of work	Self-knowledge experience element	Indicators of "self-awareness"	Levels of formation of the experience of self-knowledge	Situation	Methods, techniques, practices
Phenomenological	Knowledge on one's consciousness content	The experience of non-judgmental acceptance of one's consciousness content	Body-physiological, emotional-psychological	Self-observation situation	Contemplation, learning body metaphors, working with objects, dialogue

Cognitive	Knowledge on the functions of your consciousness	The experience of distinguishing the functions of one's consciousness	Cognitive-linguistic	Introspection Situation	Content analysis of speech and sign systems, narrative practices, dialogue
Creative	Knowledge on the structure of one's consciousness	The experience of a conscious choice of an inner position	Activity-creative	Self-governance situation	The creation of text, design, dialogue, working out a self-development program

Table 1. Model of formation of the future teacher's experience of self-discovery

At the “phenomenological” stage of working with students the main goal was to gain knowledge on the content of one's consciousness. The questions of a dialogue were directed on the content of the inner world (desires, experiences, states, sensations, emotions, thoughts, attitudes, beliefs) in accordance with a specific educational situation. These are “what?” questions. At the “cognitive” stage the goal was to study one's own functions of consciousness (attention, perception, thinking, memory). Here the “how?” the questions were raised - it was required to carry out reflection of the process of awareness. The goal of the third stage, “creative”, was to reach the level of understanding by students of their position and themselves as a self-cognition system. The joint work with students was based on a dialogue that presented in the educational process at different stages of self-reflection. This work allowed students to “read” and learn more about themselves on the physical, psychological and spiritual levels.

In our work the author's projective tests were used – “Self-perception”, “My masks and roles”, “My School”, “I am a teacher”, “The color of my professionalism”, “The Tale of the Hero”, “My pedagogical coat of arms”, “Master's profile my life” and others. These testes were used both as diagnostic techniques and educational material.

Results

If, as it was already mentioned, at the ascertaining stage, the students' experience of self-discovery was at a rather low level and was limited to a listing of external attributes, characteristics and ratings. Then at the stage of the completion of the experiment the future teachers demonstrated a different level.

In particular, in the course of discourse analysis, as well as observations and conversations, the following results were determined: the experience of non-judgmental acceptance of oneself and one's internal processes (bodily-physiological, emotional-psychological level) – 78% of students; the experience in distinguishing the nature of their attention, thinking, linguistic constructions (cognitive-linguistic level) – 69%; the experience of reflecting on their identifications and a conscious choice of the internal position of a self-discovery subject (activity-creative level) – 60%.

In the course of the study, we found a relationship between self-discovery as a bearer of the content, functions, structure of professional consciousness and the ability to put into practice the humanitarian principle of education.

This relationship was identified among undergraduate and postgraduate students based on the analysis of their lessons, public speeches, resumes, essays, presentations, videos, programs of professional and personal self-development. The results are as follows: “self-discovery” (a sufficient level of psychological intelligence) of future teachers who took part in the experiment has an influence on their ability to conduct a dialogue with the child, on their well-being and changes in professional and personal life.

In addition to positive changes in undergraduate and postgraduate students in their studies we found out other indicators of their personal development: the improvement of their well-being, an increased interest in professional and personal development, an increased initiative, activity in humanitarian researches and projects.

As an example that allows us to see the dynamics of the development of professional and personal growth, we will cite the answer of the beginning teacher Natalia S. She describes herself before starting our work as follows: “I worried about a lot of things, how to cope with different tasks and overcome a feeling of inner chaos. I was exhausted; the energy was “leaking”. I wanted to give more knowledge to the children. ... And misunderstanding of the behavior of some parents (resentment, aggression, unwillingness to take responsibility)”. In two years she describes: “Now I am already ranking the goals and objectives, I realize their significance. I consciously practice non-assessment, emotionless marks: I don't resist and don't feel resentment to my students. Some my colleagues also have the same reactions. I think the emotional behavior and background of the teacher are changing the children's reactions. Now I accept any situation, any adult or child with gratitude. I take them all as my teachers. I learnt to save energy. I “feel” my attention, I understand what I am saying now and for what goal. If earlier emotions, anxiety, fussiness prevailed more (WHAT was this for me?), now I realize the value of every moment of life.

I have even changed my gait, the moment of eating. I watch more, listen more, trying to understand what this situation is for. I see how children are changing both personally and academically".

The results of our research are at final stage and have been partially introduced into practice in the form of discipline content and educational programs at Kalmyk State University.

The developed textual-dialogical form of work with undergraduate and postgraduate students associated with the formation of their experience of self-discovery is implemented in the process of studying a number of academic disciplines in accordance with project activities at the bachelor's and master's degrees.

When we speak on the experience of self-discovery as a humanitarian constituent of the content of education we mean the experience of self-reflection in its process.

Such reflection that correlate with various types of basic cognitive processes manifests itself at various levels of the cognitive hierarchy of human consciousness. We develop it through the concepts of self-awareness, self-perception, self-representations, "self-directed" attention, meta-mind ("memory of memory"), meta-thinking ("thinking about thinking").

As a source element of the model for the formation of a future teacher's experience of self-discovery we determined the following criteria: 1) the need to learn oneself as a subject of consciousness, relationships and activity; 2) knowledge on one's own cognitive processes (content, functions and structure of one's self-awareness); 3) the ability to hold one's conscious attention on three objects of cognition in educational situation (cognizable, cognizing, cognition process).

During the experiment a system of diagnostic techniques was developed for monitoring the process under study in accordance with the definite criteria.

Discussion

In the context of universal digitalization and expansion of the influence of information technologies in education the role of teacher as a transmitter of knowledge is declining.

Nowadays the role of teacher as the organizer of human communication between participants of educational process and as the creator of "living knowledge" is growing (Zinchenko, 1998). Technology cannot replace interaction between teacher and student.

In modern socio-cultural situation, when there is a danger of "hacking a man" (Harari, 2019) but not computers, when "human-like" systems and technologies of education are in demand as they would not be in conflict with human nature and idea of life (Capra, 2002), the teacher must become the bearer of humanitarian values and humanitarian principles as special quality of education.

We consider the humanitarian principle as a regulatory phenomenon that allows us to take into account the peculiarities of human nature, to correlate with the logic of the deployment of consciousness / self-awareness in design of educational systems, processes and technologies. It also represents the idea of balance: non-interference in the individual's inner world and influence on its value-semantic sphere at the same time. This teacher should know himself or herself. He or she is to accumulate sufficient experience of self-discovery that leads to psychological intelligence.

Psychological rationality (Appelbaum, 1973; Seager, 2006) presupposes the ability for introspection and self-reflection, knowledge of the content of experiences, emotional involvement in construction of an I-image, deep understanding of another person, willingness to changes. The teacher's personality, his or her psychological mindedness, his or her "energy", thinking, consciousness (self-awareness) is the main "tool" in profession.

According to Yamburg (2011), the majority of teachers continue to be "lesson-giver" rather than "child experts", but it is difficult to blame teachers for this as "no one taught them this".

In pedagogical universities we can see the prevalence of theoretical knowledge over practical skills. Graduates of pedagogical universities come to school with the knowledge of subject but not themselves. Unfortunately, the problems of self-knowledge, self-discovery are not studied properly at universities.

A survey of university graduates who work at school now demonstrates that the majority of them lack the training received at the university, knowledge about the child, skills in interacting with children, parents and colleagues.

As a result of projective tests (Wartegg test, 1939), as well as in various questionnaires, conversations and interviews with students of the Pedagogical Faculty of Kalmyk State University (400 people were surveyed), it was revealed that there is high level of anxiety about the forthcoming work at school. Their reflective field is not sufficiently worked out and they have rather fragmentary, incomplete knowledge on their own inner world.

The analysis of the works on humanitarization of professional education (Belova, 2007; Isaev, 2013; Senko, 2017), it was revealed that the problem of elaboration of a humanitarian constituent of education content is connected with self-discovery and self-awareness of future teacher.

The analysis of previous studies shows the experience of self-discovery at the level of an empirical personality in pedagogy has not been properly studied. In fact, the question of cognition of self-discovery tool has not been worked out yet.

The difficulty lies in the fact that these processes concern the personality and often do not lend themselves to rationalization, measure. The personality is considered to be an object and a subject of cognition. He or she knows himself or herself "with the help of himself or herself". This experience of future teachers' cognition of their own cognitive structures and cognitive processes, cognition of the tools of self-discovery requires a thorough study in terms of methodology of humanitarian cognitive science.

The search for opportunities to train a teacher at university who is ready to implement the humanitarian principle in his or her activities requires new scientific knowledge from the view of the education anthropology. The anthropology of education is considered as a synthesized system of different typological knowledge on the practice of growth of "human dignity in a person" (Isaev, 2013). Such knowledge can be obtained in the context of anthropopractice known as a humanitarian practice with the aim to develop all fundamental human abilities.

The essence of anthropopractice is represented in the designing of real-life situations in which person's self-determination and the acquisition of subjectivity by him seem possible. We rely on the fact that humanitarian values are formed on the basis of freedom as a source of learning new reality (Tulchinsky, 2005). Humanitarian knowledge is the knowledge on subjective reality, human activity and is characterized by a personal character, uniqueness, emotional condition. The humanitarian principle which is denoted as a regulator in the construction of the content and process of education allows to save the unity of non-interference in the inner world of a person and the influence on his value-semantic sphere (Belova, 2007).

Considering pedagogical activity in the context of the anthropology of education, we define the experience of self-discovery as a "unit" of humanitarian knowledge, an element of professional consciousness and a humanitarian constituent of the professional education content of future professional teacher.

Speaking about the humanitarian constituent of educational content, we mean the content that, according to Senko (2017), "is not given but included". It is created in the dialogue of cultures - not only the "recognized" culture presented in textbooks but also in culture of student and teacher.

The culture of teacher in this case implies the existence in pedagogical activity at the “sociological”, “culturological”, “anthropological”, “personological”, “metaphysical” levels (Tulchinsky, 2005), when he or she is able to perceive someone (himself or herself, a child) in accordance with social connections, cultural values, essential integrity, uniqueness and freedom of spirit.

In the context of the humanitarian model of education (Belova, 2007), the content of education is represented by three components: the experience of self-awareness, the experience of dialogical relations, the experience of cultural creation. The mechanism for mastering such types of experience is textual-dialogical activity that consists of transforming of impersonal educational information into an author-address text and in dialogical comprehension of the text.

Conclusion

The study revealed that the experience of a person's cognition of content, functions and the structure of his or her consciousness is a complex process of self-observation, introspection, self-management in the context of textual-dialogical educational activity and study of the spiral-dynamic method of self-discovery.

As a humanitarian constituent of professional education content the experience of self-discovery requires the selection of special means and methods of its improvement. The results of the investigation demonstrate that the means and methods must be studied in cognitive sciences and anthropological practices (humanitarian technologies) in accordance with the analysis of the connection between body, brain and consciousness.

One of the important methods for diagnosing and forming the experience of self-discovery is the method of discourse analysis that motivates students to study their own attention as a tool for self-discovery.

The analysis of using this method at the “phenomenological”, “cognitive” and “creative” stages of working with students makes it impossible to judge its effectiveness in the process of forming of future teachers' experience of self-discovery.

Recognizing the importance of the teacher's readiness for professional activity in the context of the implementation of the humanitarian model of education, we have to assume the necessity of restructuring of educational process in preparing a future teacher at university according to key priorities.

This priority is set not by the external material that studies the personality but by its consciousness and focus on attention.

The process of student's awareness of his or her subjective reality, thinking and actions as an “instrument” of humanitarian-oriented pedagogical activity should become system-forming in the process of professional education.

In this case it provides the methods for studying pedagogical disciplines, the selection of forms and technologies of pedagogical education of a professional teacher in accordance with students’ textual-dialogical activities where they have an opportunity to explore themselves as the “author” and “addresses” of their own statements.

Undoubtedly, the problem under discussion requires further scientific investigations of many processes, in particular, the features of training teaching staff for the system of higher pedagogical education and possibilities of creating humanitarian-oriented environment at university.

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